

PSYCHOLOGY

ROLE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LEADERSHIP COMPETENCIES

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to study the relationship between emotional intelligence and leadership effectiveness in heads of educational institutions. Nowadays, emotional intelligence has become one of the key components of leadership competencies. It encompasses the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions, as well as the emotions of others, which is crucial in educational settings where interpersonal relationships are paramount. This study highlights the pressing need for professional development programs focused on enhancing emotional intelligence among educational leaders. Such programs can equip leaders with essential skills to foster a positive school climate, improve communication, and promote collaboration among staff, students, and parents. By developing emotional intelligence, leaders can better navigate challenges, resolve conflicts, and inspire their teams.

Additionally, the research underscores the correlation between high emotional intelligence and improved leadership outcomes, including increased staff morale, enhanced student performance, and more effective decision-making. It suggests that educational institutions should prioritize emotional intelligence training as part of their leadership development initiatives to cultivate more resilient and adaptive leaders.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, leadership, leadership competence, education.

Main text of the article

In today's education system, the success of educational institutions directly depends on the skills of their leaders. They play a crucial role in creating a supportive environment for effective communication between teachers, students, and parents. Therefore, in addition to their professional knowledge and management skills, emotional intelligence is essential for a successful leader.

This study aims to examine the components of emotional intelligence and its importance for effective leadership. It also explores the relationship between emotional intelligence and various aspects of leadership, such as communication, conflict resolution, and decision-making.

Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand and manage one's own emotions, as well as the emotions of others. It is an important skill for everyone, but especially for managers, as it has a significant impact on their behavior, relationships with colleagues, and interactions with the team. A leader's emotional intelligence can greatly influence the overall atmosphere and success of the team.

Daniel Goleman, in his book "Emotional Intelligence" [1], noted that people with well-developed emotional intelligence are more likely to be successful in life. People with low emotional intelligence may experience internal struggles that undermine their ability to focus on work. Goleman's research has shown that the key to a leader's effectiveness and success in an organization lies in their emotional intelligence. His work challenges traditional thinking by emphasizing the importance of emotions in evaluating a person's performance.

Schools are an important institution that shapes the future of society. Children are our future and spend a

significant portion of their lives in school. Therefore, the actions of teachers and administrators have a significant impact on student behavior. The success of a school depends on the relationships between administrators, teachers, and students, as well as the community they serve. School principals are required to maintain good relations with various parties. Directors must have emotional intelligence in order to build positive relationships with different people.

Benjamin Palmer studied 43 managers to assess the connection between emotional intelligence and leadership style [2]. He found significant correlations with several aspects of the transformational leadership model. Together, the results suggest that emotional intelligence - the ability to control and manage emotions within oneself and others - may be a fundamental competence for a leader who can transform.

Julian Barling also conducted a preliminary study on the link between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership [3]. His findings show that people with higher emotional intelligence are seen by their subordinates as exhibiting leadership behavior.

In a study conducted by Dulewich and Higgs in 1999, the researchers investigated the relationship between emotional intelligence and professional competence, focusing on the effectiveness of leadership in career growth [4]. The authors analyzed data from 58 managers in the UK and Ireland, using an emotional intelligence self-assessment tool based on a professional competence survey. They found that emotional intelligence explained more of the variance in promotion than other factors, suggesting that it plays an important role in career success.

The main purpose of this experiment is to evaluate the impact of emotional intelligence on leadership based on three key results:

1. Team performance;
2. Effectiveness of conflict resolution;
3. Employee engagement and satisfaction.

The study will test the hypothesis that leaders with higher emotional intelligence will see better results in these areas compared to leaders with lower emotional intelligence.

We have selected 2 groups of managers. Group 1 consisted of 22 with a high level of emotional intelligence, identified using standardized EI assessments. Group B consisted of 28 managers with moderate or low levels of emotional intelligence based on similar assessments.

5 employees were selected for each manager, who report directly to them. This provides a representative sample of team dynamics under different leadership styles.

Before starting the study, the level of emotional intelligence of each manager was measured using a standardized assessment of EI by Daniel Goleman. This allowed us to obtain basic data on the emotional intelligence of each leader. In addition, a basic assessment survey was conducted with the participation of team members: Team performance, levels of conflict in the team, employee satisfaction and engagement. The key findings of our analysis are summarized below:

Team performance

Group A. Teams led by managers with high EI showed significant improvement in performance, both in terms of productivity and goal attainment. Average team performance increased by 18% compared to baseline. High EI managers demonstrated greater empathy, provided regular positive feedback, and managed stress effectively, creating a positive work environment that led to increased performance.

Group B. Teams led by low EI managers showed a 6% improvement in performance, significantly lower than Group A. While there were some increases in performance, they were less consistent and more dependent on external factors. Managers with medium/low EI were more focused on task performance and less on employee motivation and emotional needs, which resulted in lower collaboration and occasional alienation among team members. Also, they tend to rely on authoritarian management styles, which results in lower levels of creativity and initiative among employees.

The results shows that higher levels of emotional intelligence in leadership are strongly associated with improved team performance.

Effectiveness of conflict resolution

Group A. High EI managers excelled at empathy and active listening, which helped team members feel heard and understood. They also used emotional regulation techniques to stay calm and focus on finding a solution. The managers of this group were able to address the underlying emotional issues causing conflicts (e.g. miscommunication, stress, or different values), not just the surface-level issues.

Group B. Managers with moderate/low EI were more focused on resolving the practical or task-oriented aspects of the conflict (e.g., performance or resource allocation issues) but often missed the emotional dynamics underlying the disputes.

When conflicts escalated, these managers had difficulty containing their emotions, sometimes resulting in more impassioned or impersonal decisions.

Employee satisfaction and engagement

Group A. Employees in teams led by high EI managers reported significantly higher levels of satisfaction and engagement. On the satisfaction survey, employees rated their leaders 20% higher in terms of emotional support and leadership effectiveness. High EI managers were more likely to provide individualized support, recognize employee achievements, and create an emotionally safe work environment. This led to higher morale and a stronger sense of team cohesion. High EI leaders were also more successful in managing team stress, which contributed to a healthier work-life balance for employees and fewer reports of burnout.

Group B. Employees under moderate/low EI managers reported lower satisfaction and engagement. On average, these employees rated their leaders 10% lower for emotional support and leadership effectiveness. While task-focused leadership was often seen as efficient, it did not foster the same level of emotional connection with employees, leading to a higher turnover intention and lower enthusiasm for work. Employees in Group B were more likely to report feeling underappreciated or disconnected from their managers, which contributed to lower motivation and engagement.

Employee satisfaction and engagement scores for Group A were significantly higher than those for Group B ($p < 0.01$), further supporting the importance of emotional intelligence in fostering positive employee experiences.

Conclusion

After analyzing the results of this study, it became clear that emotional intelligence (EI) plays a crucial role in effective leadership. Data from both Group A (high EI leaders) and Group B (medium/low EI leaders) showed significant differences in results in several key areas — team performance, conflict resolution, and employee satisfaction.

Leaders with high levels of emotional intelligence consistently outperformed their peers in these areas. Their ability to understand and manage emotions — both their own and those of their team members — contributed to smoother work, increased productivity and employee engagement. Managers with a high level of EI were also better prepared to resolve conflicts quickly and constructively, which helped to strengthen the sense of trust and cohesion in their teams.

On the other hand, while managers with medium or low EI levels could achieve results in certain areas, they faced great difficulties in building strong relationships with their teams. Conflict resolution took longer, and employee engagement was lower. These leaders often paid more attention to the tasks than the emotional dynamics of their teams, which, as the results show, can undermine long-term productivity and morale.

According to a study by Robert Kerr, John Garvin, Norma Heaton, and Emily Boyle, the data analysis reveals that individual intelligence plays a crucial role in effective leadership [5]. Specifically, employees' perceptions of a manager's performance are strongly linked to the manager's emotional intelligence (EI).

What is particularly striking is how emotional intelligence shapes not only an individual leader, but also the entire team. High-level EI managers create an environment in which employees feel supported, valued, and motivated to achieve the best results. This has the opposite effect, increasing the overall morale and satisfaction of the team, which ultimately contributes to the success of the organization.

As we move forward, this research reinforces the idea that emotional intelligence is not just a "pleasant" trait, but a fundamental leadership skill. Organizations seeking to create highly effective teams and a positive workplace culture should prioritize emotional intelligence in their leadership development programs. It's not just about teaching leaders' technical skills, but also about helping them connect with and understand the people they lead. Emotional intelligence is the key to making such connections, and as this study shows, that's the difference between a good leader and an outstanding one.

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